

National Open Access Monitor Advisory Group: Visualisations Review

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This form is to capture the National Open Access Monitor Advisory Group preferences of the options presented by OpenAIRE in the *National Open Access Report for Ireland Visualisation Samples* document: https://maynoothuniversity-my.sharepoint.com/:b:/g/personal/catherine_ferris_mu_ie/Ec02CUF-901JvKG-Ap7Ir50BPb9n-4t9DM1-k-JE5zcVIA?e=UoamcN

Please complete by COB on 4th December 2023.

1. Your Name * Required

2. Please state your preference: * Required

- Option 1
- Option 2
- Option 3
- Option 4
- Option 5
- Other

Visualisations Review
